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Fostering energy efficiency investments through risk assessment

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It is evident that energy efficiency (EE) investments are inherently risky. A growing body of literature has identified that this is due to the multitude of uncertainties associated with the future cash flows of EE projects, such as the price of energy and technology risk. Therefore, their risk evaluation becomes a complex procedure, while also some risk factors present a lot of difficulties to be assessed, such as missing information and subjectivity. Financial institutions avoid evaluating the presence and potential severity of EE risks in detail and especially for small scale projects, due to the entailed high transaction costs. As a consequence, EE projects tend to never get financed despite the fact that some of them have good properties and being profitable. Many studies exist that evaluate the impact of individual risk factors to the successful implementation of EE projects, such as the rebound effect, however, a considerable gap exists in the literature as regards the holistic risk evaluation of EE projects. This study tries to bridge this gap by proposing an analytical framework for evaluating the total risk of EE projects to fail meeting their predicted performance. In this respect, all the risk factors and uncertainties that can negatively affect the profitability of EE projects are identified and analysed, while a mix of quantitative and qualitative techniques is utilised. The methodology is applied to the main EE sectors and several Member States.

Keywords: Energy Efficiency; Finance; Investment Risks; Risk Management; Risk Assessment; Member States

